

COMPOSING WITH ACOUSTIC SPACE AS MATERIAL IN AMBISONICS

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores how Ambisonics offers a technical solution of working with acoustic space as an integral compositional element. By discussing the formats' ability to encode spatial environments that go beyond point-source paradigms, it is shown how composers can dynamically shape virtual spaces by treating acoustic space as a compositional medium rather than merely a fixed attribute of the physical space. Through historical perspectives on spatial composition, the authors contextualise the development of spatial thinking in music. The paper also links Ambisonics to the acousmatic tradition, suggesting that just as sound was freed from its source, so too can space be freed from loudspeakers and composed independently. The authors argue that by integrating virtual space into the compositional process, acoustic space itself becomes an active musical material, expanding the creative possibilities of electroacoustic and immersive music.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of scene-based audio formats such as Ambisonics has opened up new possibilities for treating acoustic space as an integral compositional element. However, the intersection of spatial audio and composition also reveals a complex terminology, beginning with the 'obscure'¹ concept of 'space' itself: „English terminology is notoriously imprecise about space, confusing and overlapping the meanings of words which it may well be useful to disentangle and imbue with some more specific definitions in this context: position, place, placement, location, localisation, situation and even space itself.“ [2]

For the purpose of this work, the authors define space, be it virtual or physical, as the acoustic architecture determined by room acoustics, the study of how sound behaves in an enclosed space, including reflections, absorption, diffusion and room modes, which affect clarity, intelligibility, and overall sound quality.

In [3] Smalley coins the terms listening and composed space to differentiate between physical and non-physical spaces. However, in his later publication [4] he already mentioned that in acousmatic music, space can be included: "But with acousmatic music in public contexts,

¹ "If there is an obscure value, it is certainly that of space." François Bayle in [1]

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the spatial image can liberate itself from the physical presence of the listening space – it can escape its arena." He concludes that the distinction between listening and composed spaces is no longer ideal, given that the acoustics of a listening space can be virtual.

Therefore the authors chose the terms physical and virtual space, to differentiate between these two acoustic spaces.

1.1 Foundational Works of Composing with Space

Composing with space has always interested composers, although their approaches and dedication to this element have varied significantly across different periods. Already during the Renaissance, musicians were placed in spatially separated groups in order to intensify dynamics and create echo effects through softer repetitions in different groups. In the famous motet *Spem in Alium* by Thomas Tallis, the eight groups of 40 voices were placed around the listener. This was also common in the Baroque period, but such spatial arrangements of musicians seem to have been forgotten in the classical music era. Since then, the way in which composers deal with space in their works has changed considerably, as the brief descriptions of the following two selected works will show.

In several works, most notably the series 'Music for Sound Joined Rooms', which began in 1980, Maryanne Amacher explored the sound and atmosphere of different spaces. Her approach, which considered space, sound and perception as inseparable units, continues to influence experimental music and sound art today. From her artistic statement: "The idea is to create an atmosphere that gives the drama of being inside a cinematic close-up, a form of "sonic theater" in which architecture magnifies the sensorial presence of experience. Rooms, walls, and corridors that sing."²

Alvin Lucier's "I Am Sitting in a Room" from 1969 is a performative work that showcased space in a different way, as it was also pointed out by Helga de la Motte-Haber in 'Space Impression Mediated by Sound' [5]: "I distinguish, therefore, between two different artistic intentions: on the one hand, sound represented in space, and on the other, space presented in sound. There are very few composers who present the exterior space by sound. It always seems necessary to make recourse to the music of Alvin Lucier [...]". In this work, Lucier excited the surrounding space by repeatedly recording and playing back his voice. This not only resulted in a complete 'disintegration' of the

² <https://www.foundationforcontemporaryarts.org/recipients/maryanne-amacher/>

recorded voice, but also brought the room modes to the foreground in a way similar to the excitation of a musical instrument. This performance was probably the first time that the acoustic space itself became an instrument, highlighting its specific geometry and characteristics.

Another major composition where the focus is not only on working with acoustic space but on working with it as a malleable medium, is Luigi Nono's *Prometeo: Tragedia dell'ascolto* [6]. For the Venice premiere in 1984, architect Renzo Piano created a special wooden 'ark' inside the church of San Lorenzo that functioned as an independent instrument, housing both musicians and audience. Sound emanated from all directions - sides, top and bottom - deliberately deconstructing the traditional frontal listening experience and breaking with conventional concert formats that separate stage and audience.

Although Ambisonics was still in its infancy during Nono's time, 'Prometeo' shows conceptual parallels in its thinking about soundfields rather than individual loudspeakers or sound objects. The subtitle of the work, "Tragedy of Listening", emphasises concentrated listening, free from visual references, a core aspect of acousmatic approaches, which will be discussed in Section 4. Nono wrote the score independently of specific technical implementations, requiring adaptation for different performance venues (a problem that Higher Order Ambisonics largely solves). Importantly, Nono's spatial concept isn't realistic in terms of reproducing physical spaces, but instead creates a poetic, abstract spatiality. Through the movement and distortion of sound, he created an 'experienced space' different from the architectural environment, transcending physical boundaries to create sound environments that are physically impossible, or at least unrealistic.

In the aforementioned works, space was primarily considered in physical terms, focusing on how to combine or trace it in different ways. In this publication, however, we aim to highlight a different approach to space, viewing it as an integral part of the composition. This involves working firstly with virtual spaces and secondly, directly integrating the space into the composition and the medium. This aspect will be explored further in Section 2.

The next chapter introduces the Ambisonics format, and with it the new compositional approaches that have accompanied this technological breakthrough in the context of composition with space.

1.2 Ambisonics and Scene-Based Audio

Ambisonics is a scene-based audio format that describes audio such as music or complex soundfields, by projecting it onto a sphere, much like a display in which the listener sits in its center. A fixed number of audio channels, as defined by the Ambisonics order, in the form of spherical harmonics are used to describe the soundfield. As with visual screen resolution, the higher the Ambisonics order and the greater the number of spherical harmonics used, the higher the spatial resolution of the sound scene. For loudspeaker

playback, the order in which the sound is reproduced also determines the size of the sweet spot, or the area in which sound localization remains stable for a greater number of listeners [7].

Typically, Ambisonics is used in 3rd up to 7th order, the number of channels required is given by 2^{n+1} , where n represents the order. For Ambisonics playback, the scene is decoded for a specific loudspeaker configuration, whether it is a setup with many evenly distributed loudspeakers, a 7.1.4-loudspeaker configuration, or headphones.

This brings several advantages. In comparison to channel-based audio, having a universal scene format that is not tied to a specific loudspeaker setup allows for playback on any configuration, even when it differs from the original setup. This also means that spatial audio can be produced on headphones and played back on a multichannel loudspeaker system without significant trade-offs, apart from the room-related conflicts discussed in Section 5.

The difference between scene-based and object-based audio lies in the fundamental philosophy of describing the soundfield. In object-based audio, this is achieved by creating multiple sound objects, each of which is attributed spatial information. Therefore, the number of objects used directly determines the number of channels needed. In Ambisonics, the necessary number of audio channels is determined by the order used, regardless of how many objects or 'sound sources' are encoded, since the channels are only used to describe the soundfield in the form of spherical harmonics. This makes Ambisonics particularly well-suited to describing complex scenes, such as those within a room.

2. ACOUSTIC SPACE WITHIN THE MEDIUM

Despite the many liberations in music during the 20th century, the constraint and dependence on physical space remains a limitation given the importance of acoustic space and its expressive potential. The ability of the Ambisonics format to describe an acoustic scene within the medium, as discussed in the previous Section, addresses the issue of dependence on physical architecture. Ambisonics now makes it possible to integrate the acoustic space into the medium by encoding its reflections, diffusion and room modes. Acoustic space becomes an essential element, included directly into the composition and the fixed media file, rather than relying solely on the physical space, offers significant possibilities. As Blesser et al. are stating in [8]: "In this new art form, the aural architecture of a virtual space is more important than the architecture of a real space."

Most importantly, acoustic space becomes virtual and therefore highly controllable, enabling composers to think purely in acoustic scenes rather than relying on channels or objects to create the scene. This shift raises significant questions, such as the need to define an ideal physical space. This important aspect will be explored further in Section 5.

Thinking of space within the medium is especially beneficial for binaural playback. This virtual space significantly

enhances spatial perception, compensating for the typical absence of physical space.

Thinking about sound in scenes helps to recognize that sound and space are inseparable. One cannot exist without the other, there is no sound without space, and likewise, acoustic space cannot be perceived without sound, as also stated by Catena et al. in [9]: "When listening to a piano in a concert hall, or when we hear a bird singing in the forest, whatever spatial information is in the sound - the reverberation of the concert hall or the density of the forest is embedded and becomes an integral part of the perception of the sound." This interdependence describes the importance of integrating both into the compositional process, and will be explored in the following sections.

3. SPATIALIZING SOUND

Traditionally, when working with a loudspeaker orchestra, also known as an Acousmonium, spatialization is achieved by diffusing a stereo or multichannel track across several loudspeakers in the physical space during a performance. Object-based audio spatialization is primarily about positioning or moving sound objects in space to create distinct perceived directions. The authors therefore suggest distinguishing between two distinct concepts in spatialization: firstly, the creation of acoustic space and secondly, the creation of movement in space. While the latter is more concrete, the former is at least as important and is also the focus of this text.

Significant efforts are currently being made to maximize the perception of sound direction, using virtual space to enhance spatial perception. Treating sounds as points in space, as in object-based audio formats, supports the idea that the purpose of space is only to support the perception of sound position. In a musical context, however, acoustic space offers much more than the ability to perceive the direction of individual instruments, just as good concert halls are not defined by the ability to perceive the exact position of individual instruments. Instead of viewing space merely as a container for sound objects, we can consider it as a quality of sound, a perspective that will be further explored in Section 3.2.

3.1 The Point-in-Space Paradigm

Working with Ambisonics enables composers to think very differently of sounds in space, one that is much closer to actual perception, as pointed out by Ulf Holbrook: "In the real-world, sound does not exist as a point. Sound produced by a source will propagate outward to the surrounding space, and we will experience different frequency reflections and time decays from a series of surfaces in the space surrounding us." [10]. Disconnecting sounds from loudspeakers and thus freeing the compositional intent from the medium is a common thought in contemporary instrumental music as well, where working with sound and timbre comes first and the choice of instrument later. A quote from a talk held by Clara Ianotta

comes to mind: "I don't care about the instruments I have in front of me." (Impuls Festival Graz 2025). Concluding from that, it may be a better way not to think of sound objects that are being placed in space, but of a sound scene, that emerges by the interaction between sound and space. This transforms the composers from someone who previously placed sounds in space to an architect of imaginary spaces.

The belief that technical tools alone can solve this paradigm is a misunderstanding. The famous quote from Iannis Xenakis comes to mind when talking about technology at the service of art: "[...] hope of an extraordinary aesthetic success based on extraordinary technology is a cruel deceit." [11].

Most Ambisonics encoders that function at the same time as panning devices give the user the possibility to move a point (the sound source) in a polar or cartesian coordinate system. Only when combining tools (like the RoomEncoder and GranularEncoder) it is possible to work in a different but still very abstract way. This gets confirmed by Barrett in [12]: "Yet as the popularity of Ambisonics and other spatialisation techniques has increased, many of the tools available encourage a 'point in space' rather than 'image in space' way of working; an approach that inhibits the development of the sound object as a spatial element in the compositional process." In this context, the following statement by Ulf Holbrook is very relevant: "The thinking around the composition of sound images, rather than the single point in space, is integral if the use of spatial audio is to have any relevance outside of novelty". [10].

3.2 Constructing Virtual Scenes

Acoustic space refers to the aurally perceived architectural environment in which sounds exist and interact. Both real and virtual environments follow psychoacoustic principles that influence our spatial perception.

Virtual environments can be created from scratch using Ambisonics, as explained in Section 2. This enables the creation and manipulation of acoustic spaces from the ground up. Within these virtual spaces, acoustic properties such as reverberation time, timbre and diffuseness can be precisely adjusted. In this context, acoustic space becomes a dynamic, flexible medium.

The concept of spaces that change in size, shape, or other characteristics over time, or expand to unrealistic magnitudes, goes beyond theoretical possibilities. It becomes a concrete compositional tool. This shift aligns with the notion of 'composing space,' where sound and space are no longer treated as separate elements but are integrated into a unified architectural experience.

In order to avoid relying too heavily on technical tools alone, the compositional process needs to be preceded by a consideration of perception and psychoacoustics. As pointed out by Barrett as well: "[...] despite a considerable development in the technological tools available for the spatialisation of sound, this has not materialised in the

electroacoustic music we hear nowadays in concerts. [...] the understanding of spatial issues among composers is still not so advanced.” [13].

One possible approach to creating such a virtual space would be to analyze the behaviour of physical rooms in terms of frequency and time. The Ambisonics RoomEncoder from the IEM plugin suite³, for example, shown in Figure 1, can be used to generate the early reflections of a room.

Figure 1. RoomEncoder plugin: The timing sequence of reflections is displayed at the bottom.

It synthesizes up to 200 wavefronts, the direct sound from the source to the receiver in the specified direction, as well as all the reflections coming from the correct direction as in a room. While rendering such a large number of reflections is typically not recommended, it demonstrates the potential and flexibility of a scene-based format.

In addition to early reflection synthesis, a diffuse late reverb is required. One possibility is the FDN-Reverb from the same plugin suite, as it allows audio input in the Ambisonics domain. However, common reverb plugins can also be encoded into the Ambisonics format, therefore, the same plugin can be used for different directions, but it must be ensured that decorrelation between each channel is achieved.

After defining the virtual acoustic space, which represents the static part of the spatialization, movement or abstract directional patterns can be encoded into the scene. This is achieved by using, among other solutions from the SPARTA [14] and ICST suite⁴, the StereoEncoder or the GranularEncoder from the IEM plugin-suite, one of which is shown in Figure 2. Unlike the RoomEncoder, these types of encoder do not aim to reproduce a realistic room, but rather movement or static sounds and can complement the acoustic space.

Blessier et al. describe in [8] the process of spatialization as follows: ”Anyone who creates a complete sound field that produces the experience of spatiality is functioning as an aural architect. Traditionally, sound sources from

Figure 2. GranularEncoder plugin: Converts a mono track into grains encoded in the Ambisonics format.

loudspeakers were viewed as injecting sonic events into a listening space, but with the advent of surround-sound reproduction, the sound field includes, and in some cases, replaces the experience of the listening space.” [8].

4. ACOUSMATIC THINKING AND AMBISONICS

Bearing in mind the background of Pythagoras teaching behind a curtain so that the students could concentrate on his oral explanations, the term acousmatic can be used in a different context.⁵ First proposed by Jerome Peignot in 1955 and then further developed by Pierre Schaeffer, it liberated sounds from their sources. They can or even should be perceived as sounds themselves without context, coined as reduced listening by Schaeffer in *Traité des Objets Musicaux* (1966).

That the acousmatic thinking has a special meaning for the composition with spatialization and virtual spaces as well, is pointed out by Blessier et al. in [8]: ”Acousmatic music is ideal for free-form auditory imagery, sound metamorphoses, and virtual spaces. It is designed to be unconstrained by, as well as decoupled from, visual cues that would otherwise dominate or undermine the validity of the intended auditory images, including the image of a particular space.”

The historical context of French and Belgian acousmatic composers such as François Bayle and Annette Vandé Gorne, whose thinking stems mainly from the work with the Acousmonium, emphasizes loudspeakers in the original sense: like human speakers with different voices/tones, they stimulate the acoustics of a concert hall differently depending on their position. In addition, most Acousmoniums are restricted to a frontal presentation of the loudspeakers, creating a sound scene is not the main focus of this acousmatic branch.

⁵ A different perspective on how the metaphor of Pythagoras curtain can be used is mentioned in [15]: ”For many years the loudspeaker was seen more like an acoustic window to another world, that of an idealised performance space, maybe a real hall without audience or a specialized space adjacent to the recording studio. We were looking at the Pythagorean veil, which covered the visual contact with the sound’s apparent source. So the cause was taken to be the Berlin Philharmonic somehow performing >behind< the loudspeakers.”

³ <https://plugins.iem.at/>

⁴ <https://ambisonics.ch/icst-ambisonics-plugins/>

The ideal in Ambisonics configurations on the other hand is to hide the loudspeakers completely (behind an 'acousmatic curtain'), to free the soundfield from them in such a way that it is no longer connected to the speakers.

If we now begin to think in "terms of Ambisonics", which means that sounds are no longer related to loudspeakers but can together form a soundfield or, more precisely, a space, we can imagine the space itself as an acousmatic medium. In the same way that the composers of the GRM group around Schaeffer separated sounds from their contexts, in working with Ambisonics we have the possibility of liberating sounds and their corresponding spaces from their specific reproduction medium. If space is acousmatic, it means that the listener perceives it as a compositional element that does not necessarily have a reference to the real world. Space as an invisible but active medium that can be freely shaped by the composer.

As Barrett states in [12]: "In post-Schaefferian acousmatic music space has taken centre stage. Many composers would now regard space and spatialisation to be the unique quality that sets acousmatic music apart from other contemporary music genres."

5. DISCUSSION

While there are many compelling reasons for transferring acoustic space into the virtual realm, this paper has not addressed the fact that physical space 'still exists', meaning that virtual and physical spaces will inevitably overlap. The challenge is to ensure that they merge seamlessly.

As Smalley puts it: "This superimposition of spaces can create 'consonant' or 'dissonant' relationships between composed and listening environments changing indicative interpretations to an extent often not envisaged or even considered by the composer, bringing the intimate into the large, the large into the larger, the vast into the small, must be influential." [3]. This means the better a format like Ambisonics conveys the impression of space from medium to medium, from listening to performing space (be it a concert hall or headphones), the greater the chance of a 'consonant relationship between the composed space and the listening space', or in our terms virtual space and physical space.

Being able to work with virtual acoustic spaces in the compositional work, means that concert venues such as the Cube at the IEM Graz or the Klangdom at the ZKM Karlsruhe are much less reverberant than 'classical' concert halls and thus more easily create consonant relationships between composed and listening space.

That this question is maybe not as problematic as it seems, was stated by Kendall et al.: "Interestingly, the scale of the audio scene is independent of the physical scale of the audio reproduction system. We have learned to accept the sizing of audio reproduction systems as analogous to the sizing of TV screens—we adjust our spatial frame of reference to the system." [16]. Blesser et al. also confirm this impression: "The electronic disconnection of sounds from their familiar origins presented listeners with an unfamiliar experience of music and its space, and with the cognitive

burden of acquiring an appreciation for virtual spaces. After a half century of exposure to these new art forms, many listeners now have sufficient experience to accept virtual spaces as the norm." [8].

In binaural headphone playback, physical acoustic space is effectively non-existent. Therefore virtual space compensates that missing space, as mentioned in Section 3.2. The lack of space in binaural headphone reproduction, as opposed to playback using multiple loudspeakers, forces one to consider scene and space creation within a composition. This raises the question of which playback situation is correct, and what the ideal listening space should be. The discussion about whether virtual spaces like such created by binaural room impulse responses should be added for binaural Ambisonics decoding remains unresolved, but is required since defining a reference is beneficial for the community. Given Ambisonics' ability to include virtual spaces, one could argue that headphone playback should be considered the reference, making the addition of a virtual playback room redundant. This idea is supported by the fact that physical rooms will always vary and are hard to standardize. It still needs to be investigated whether physical space is counterproductive when composed for a purely space-less playback situations, such as with headphones.

6. CONCLUSION

The function of Ambisonics in the context of spatial composition to redefine the role of space in electroacoustic and immersive music has been highlighted. Rather than treating space as a passive container for sound, Ambisonics allows for the integration of spatial elements as an active component of the compositional process. By encoding entire acoustic environments instead of individual sound sources, composers can shape dynamic spatial architectures that evolve throughout a piece.

This shift challenges conventional paradigms of spatialization that rely solely on point-source models. Instead, Ambisonics supports a scene-based approach, where space and sound interact as interdependent elements. Such an approach enables new aesthetic possibilities, from the creation of immersive environments to the manipulation of perceived spatial depth and movement. The concept of 'room in medium' further expands these possibilities, allowing for virtual acoustic spaces that are not constrained by physical performance environments.

The parallels between Ambisonics and acousmatic thinking reinforce the idea that sound, and the acoustic space that accompanies it, can be detached from its physical origin and shaped independently. This perspective opens up new ways of composing and listening, where spatial structures are no longer secondary to musical material but become intrinsic to the compositional language itself.

With every new possibility in composition, new techniques have to be developed. There is much discussion about the need for new tools to complement new features (as described in Section 3.1). But the basic functions are already covered by several VST plugin-suites, and as with any development of new compositional possibilities, it

takes time for certain practices to evolve. So now is the time to experiment with the new material, the new space, to find out how music can benefit from it.

„[...] *Space is a significant part of this liberation. When elaborated through the process of composition into the realm of performance practice, it has the power to transport us quite literally, at the speed of sound into other places, other situations and even, because of its interactions with our personal memories and histories, other times. Ultimately, therefore, it can reach deep into the most inaccessible place of all: our imagination.*“ [2]

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